

type	optional	name	showif	value	label	choice1	choice2	choice3	choice4	choice5	choice6	choice7	choice8	choice9	choice10
<p>Survey of the CoARA Working Group "Responsible Metrics and Indicators" (2025).</p> <p>The survey questions are licensed under a CC-BY-4.0 license. This means, you can reuse, modify, and redistribute the survey (or parts of it), as long as you credit the original authors. (The structure of the survey questions follows the format of the https://formr.org open source survey framework.)</p> <p>Please cite as:</p> <p>Schönbrodt, F. D., Nawrot, K., Crepaldi, D., & Heyard, R. (2025). Survey of the CoARA Working Group "Responsible Metrics and Indicators" (version 1.1). doi:10.5281/zenodo.15297248</p>															
					<p># Survey on the usage of metrics and indicators in research assessment</p> <p>The goal of the survey is to review the metrics and indicators used in member institutions of CoARA and beyond. The survey is conducted by the CoARA Working Group "Responsible Metrics and Indicators"(https://github.com/rachelHey/metricsWG) (RMI WG).</p> <p>**The aim is to investigate the status quo of how metrics and indicators are used in research assessment.** This will be a ground for preparing an integrative framework of indicator-based and qualitative research assessment. If you have any questions or concerns do not hesitate to [contact us](https://github.com/rachelHey/metricsWG). We are very grateful for your time and collaboration. The survey is open until 2025-06-08.</p> <p>**Confidentiality and open data**: We will release anonymous open data. We make sure that neither individuals nor institutions can be identified. Most questions concern practices at your institution, but some also ask for your personal opinion. Please read our [consent form](https://www.lmu.de/psy/en/chairs/methods/rmi_survey.html) and assert with the check box below that you have read it and agree to it. You can get a copy of the data you entered. Instructions will be provided in the email we send to all participants.</p> <p>In order to keep this survey short, we created a [separate document](https://docs.google.com/document/d/1qXR_s_kb76G8fPbFqRj91FwnEIZKYyXaHLpRMFFRsG/edit?usp=sharing) where we give more background information on the aims and the terminology.</p> <p>*The Steering Committee of the RMI WG*</p> <p>Davide Crepaldi (Italian Reproducibility Network) davide.crepaldi@unipv.it Rachel Heyard (Swiss Reproducibility Network) rachel.heyard@uzh.ch Katarzyna Nawrot (University of Warsaw) ka.nawrot2@uw.edu.pl (Co-Chair of the RMI WG) Felix Schönbrodt (German Psychological Society) felix.schoenbrodt@psy.lmu.de (Co-Chair of the RMI WG)</p>										
note		note_Info1													
note		note_Info2													
note		note_Info3			<p><details> <summary> We only consider <i>research</i> activities. (click for more) </summary> We only consider indicators for the evaluation of research activities (i.e., we do not consider indicators for other academic activities, such as teaching, administration, or leadership performance). </details></p>										
check_button	!	consent_check			I have read the [consent form](https://www.psy.lmu.de/pm/consent/rmi-study.html) and agree to it.										
submit		submit_welcome			Continue to next page ...										
note		note_GeneralInformation			### General information										
text		Institution_Name			Name of the institution										
text		Website			Website of the institution										
email	!	Email			Your email address. We need this to send you the invitation to the next part of the survey. *Note: Gmail is very aggressive in blocking (apparent) spam. If possible, use an institutional email.*										
text		Position			In which function are you answering the survey? (e.g., for a specific faculty or subunit; for the whole institution, or for a specific office)										
mc_button		CoARA_member			Is your institution a CoARA member?	Yes	No								
mc_button	*	CoARA_action_plan	CoARA_member==1		Did your organization already publish your action plan?	Yes	No	I don't know							
select_one		Institution_Type			What is the type of the institution you are representing?	An entire University	A department/faculty within a University	School of Higher Education	A department/faculty within a School of Higher Education	Scientometric organization	Evaluation organization	Funding organization	Academic society	Grassroot Network / Reproducibility Network	Other
select_one		University_Type	Institution_Type==1 Institution_Type==2		Please specify the type of University:	General University	Art University	Economic University	Life Science University	Medical University	Technical University				
text		Institution_Type_Subunit	Institution_Type==2 Institution_Type==4		Please specify the department/faculty you are representing:										
text		Institution_Other	Institution_Type==8		Please specify:										
text	*	Discipline			If you are answering the survey from the perspective of a specific discipline, please specify:										
select_one		OwnershipStructure			Ownership structure of your institution:	Public/non-commercial institution	Commercial institution	Other							

type	optional	name	showif	value	label	choice1	choice2	choice3	choice4	choice5	choice6	choice7	choice8	choice9	choice10
text		OwnershipStructure_Other	OwnershipStructure==3		Please specify:										
select_one		Institution_Size			If you have the numbers quickly at hand: Size of your institution in approximate number of active researchers (Professors & Postdocs, not counting PhD students).	1-9	10-49	50-99	100-249	250-499	500 and more	Does not apply	I don't know		
select_one		Institution_Students			Size of your institution in approximate number of students.	1-99	100-499	500-1000	1000-9999	10000-19999	20000 and more	We have no students / does not apply	I don't know		
select_one		Location			In which country is your institution (primarily) based?	Specific country	International institution								
text		Location_Country	Location==1		Please specify:										
mc_multiple		MI_Use			How are indicators used in your institution? (Select all that apply)										
note		Evaluation_Units			What are the "units" of evaluation?										
mc_button		Evaluation_Units_Outputs			Specific research "outputs" (e.g., papers, data sets, projects)	Yes	No								
mc_multiple		Evaluation_Purpose_Outputs	Evaluation_Units_Outputs==1		What is the purpose of evaluation? (multiple choice)	Academic graduation (i.e., PhD, habilitation, other)	Academic hiring	Job promotion to a higher payment level	Performance-oriented payments and rewards	Awards	Funding decisions	General performance evaluation (e.g. an institutional evaluation)	Periodic evaluation and feedback	Certificates of excellence	Position in rankings
text	*	Evaluation_Purpose_Outputs_Other	Evaluation_Units_Outputs==1		Other purposes of evaluation (optional):										
mc_button		Evaluation_Units_Persons			Individual "researchers" (i.e., persons)	Yes	No								
mc_multiple		Evaluation_Purpose_Outputs_2	Evaluation_Units_Persons==1		What is the purpose of evaluation? (multiple choice)	Academic graduation (i.e., PhD, habilitation, other)	Academic hiring	Job promotion to a higher payment level	Performance-oriented payments and rewards	Awards	Funding decisions	General performance evaluation (e.g. an institutional evaluation)	Periodic evaluation and feedback	Certificates of excellence	Position in rankings
text	*	Evaluation_Purpose_Outputs_Other_2	Evaluation_Units_Persons==1		Other purposes of evaluation (optional):										
mc_button		Evaluation_Units_Teams			Larger "groups" of researchers (i.e., teams)	Yes	No								
mc_multiple		Evaluation_Purpose_Outputs_3	Evaluation_Units_Teams==1		What is the purpose of evaluation? (multiple choice)	Academic graduation (i.e., PhD, habilitation, other)	Academic hiring	Job promotion to a higher payment level	Performance-oriented payments and rewards	Awards	Funding decisions	General performance evaluation (e.g. an institutional evaluation)	Periodic evaluation and feedback	Certificates of excellence	Position in rankings
text	*	Evaluation_Purpose_Outputs_Other_3	Evaluation_Units_Teams==1		Other purposes of evaluation (optional):										
mc_button		Evaluation_Units_Institutions			Entire "institutions" or large subunits (departments, universities)	Yes	No								
mc_multiple		Evaluation_Purpose_Outputs_4	Evaluation_Units_Institutions==1		What is the purpose of evaluation? (multiple choice)	Academic graduation (i.e., PhD, habilitation, other)	Academic hiring	Job promotion to a higher payment level	Performance-oriented payments and rewards	Awards	Funding decisions	General performance evaluation (e.g. an institutional evaluation)	Periodic evaluation and feedback	Certificates of excellence	Position in rankings
text	*	Evaluation_Purpose_Outputs_Other_4	Evaluation_Units_Institutions==1		Other purposes of evaluation (optional):										
mc_button		MI_Impact			In your opinion, how high is the impact of indicators on decisions and/or rankings within your assessment exercise?	High	Medium	Low	Insignificant						
mc_multiple		MI_Impact_AnswerBase			↳ What is your answer based on?	official documents	participation in meetings and committees	your own experience as a subject of assessment	small talk with colleagues	other					
text		MI_Impact_AnswerBase_Other	MI_Impact_AnswerBase==5		Please specify:										
submit		submit_Questions			Continue to next page ...										
note		note_GeneralQuestions			## Questions on general level This part contains some questions on a general level and will only take a few minutes. You probably can skip many of the questions (by answering "don't know/not applicable") if your organisation does not perform these assessment tasks.										
note		note_AcademicGraduation			All of the following questions should be answered "from your personal point of view". We are interested in your opinion, which might not reflect any institutional view. We will not attribute your opinion to your institution.										
mc_button		AcademicGraduation_ClearProcess			### For the purpose of "academic graduation" (i.e., PhD, habilitation, other):										
mc_button					Does your institution provide clear instructions for evaluating "academic graduation"?	Fully	Mostly	Somewhat	Not at all	don't know/not applicable					

type	optional	name	showif	label	choice1	choice2	choice3	choice4	choice5	choice6	choice7	choice8	choice9	choice10	choice11	
This is Part 2 of the survey; this is assessed in a loop (once per indicator), so that participants can enter as many indicators as they want.																
				## Indicator Entry Form												
note		note_MI		Instructions: * "Indicator" and "metric" are used interchangeably. * We only consider indicators for the evaluation of "research" activities, (i.e., we do not consider indicators for other academic activities, such as teaching, administration, or leadership performance). * We are explicitly interested both in official and 'unofficial' indicators that are used in your institution, and also in indicators that are only used "locally" at your institution. If in your experience some committees regularly use unofficial indicators in their decisions, please add them. * If your organization employs "bundled indicators" (such as the French Open Science Monitor), please provide the information for each indicator "within" the bundle, that is used.												
text		MI_ShortName		Short name of the indicator												
textarea	*	MI_Description		Longer description of the indicator (please give enough detail to understand how the indicator is assessed)												
note		MI_header1		### Indicator Category												
mc		MI_Category		Please select the category that fits the most. If none of them fits at all, select "Other" and provide more information about the category below.	Counting publications	Citation-related indicators	Third-party funding	Open science / Reproducibility	Research collaborations and partnerships	Impact outside academia / visibility	Integrity & accountability service to the field	Publication quality (please specify how it is measured)	Other (please specify below)			
text	*	MI_Category_Other	MI_Category >= 8	↳ Please explain in a few words how this indicator works and what exactly is measured.												
mc		MI_Subcategory_Counting	MI_Category == 1	↳ What exactly is counted?	↳ # of overall publications	↳ # of publications in eligible journals (e.g., Q1 & Q2; A-ranking)	↳ # of first/last authorships on papers	Counting publications: Other (please specify below)								
text	*	MI_Subcategory_Counting_Other	MI_Category == 1 & MI_Subcategory_Counting == 4	↳ Please explain in a few words, what exactly is counted.												
mc		MI_Subcategory_Citation	MI_Category == 2	↳ How exactly are citations used for this indicator?	Raw citations scores	Field- and/or age normalized citation scores	h-index (original)	Variation of h-index (e.g., h_iA, g-index)	Publications in top citation classes (e.g., top 10%, top 1%)	Journal Impact Factor (e.g., aggregated across all publications)	Citation-related: Other (please specify below)					
text	*	MI_Subcategory_Citation_Other	MI_Category == 2 & MI_Subcategory_Citation == 7	↳ Please explain in a few words how this citation indicator works.												
mc		MI_Subcategory_Funding	MI_Category == 3	↳ How exactly is funding used as an indicator?	↳ # of third-party funded projects (overall)	Sum of third-party funded money	↳ # of projects from specific funders (e.g., EU-funding; only competitive funding)	Funding: Other (please specify below)								
text	*	MI_Subcategory_Funding_Other	MI_Category == 3 & MI_Subcategory_Funding == 4	↳ Please explain in a few words how this funding indicator works.												
mc		MI_Subcategory_OS	MI_Category == 4	↳ How exactly is Open Science used as an indicator?	Share of Open Access	Share of Open/FAIR data sets	Share of Open Source Code	Share of Preregistrations	Metadata records shared	Degree of scientific rigor (please specify below how it is measured)	Open Science / Reproducibility: Other (please specify below)					
text	*	MI_Subcategory_OS_Other	MI_Category == 4 & MI_Subcategory_OS >= 6	↳ Please explain in a few words how this Open Science indicator works.												
mc		MI_Subcategory_Collaboration	MI_Category == 5	↳ How exactly is Collaboration used as an indicator?	(International) collaboration	Collaboration outside academia – e.g., Triple Helix, PPP	Projects contributing to focus area (e.g., regional, strategic agenda, SDGs)	Research collaborations and partnerships: Other (please specify below)								
text	*	MI_Subcategory_Collaboration_Other	MI_Category == 5 & MI_Subcategory_Collaboration == 4	↳ Please explain in a few words how this Collaboration indicator works.												
mc		MI_Subcategory_OutImpact	MI_Category == 6	↳ How exactly is Impact outside academia measured?	Altmetrics	Societal impact	Industry impact	Policy impact	Environmental impact	Impact outside academia: Other (please specify below)						
text	*	MI_Subcategory_OutImpact_Other	MI_Category == 6 & MI_Subcategory_OutImpact == 6	↳ Please explain in a few words how this Impact indicator works.												
mc		MI_Subcategory_OutImpact_Industry	MI_Category == 6 & MI_Subcategory_OutImpact == 3	↳ How exactly is industry impact measured?	Number of patents / patent applications	Number of innovations	R&D projects with industry	Industry Impact: Other (please specify below)								

